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An Analytical Study on the Production of Horticultural Crops in Arunachal Pradesh

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Abstract

Indian agriculture can be broadly divided into crop farming, animal husbandry, horticulture, floriculture. Over the past few years, horticulture has emerged as one of the most important component of the Indian agricultural sector. India is today one of the largest producer of horticultural crops in the world and also exports a variety of fruits and vegetables to different countries. In fact, India is today the leading producer of a variety of fruits and vegetables in the world.

Keywords Production, Productivity, Horticulture crops, Arunachal Pradesh.

Introduction

Arunachal Pradesh is basically an agrarian State as majority of its people live on agriculture and allied activities like forestry, fishing, horticulture etc. At present, horticulture and tourism are considered the two potential sectors of the State. In recent years, there has been a lot of emphasis on the growth of horticulture in the State. Since there are obvious limitations to the growth of cereals and food grains in a mountainous State like Arunachal Pradesh, horticulture production, which could be taken on slopes also, is being promoted as a part of strategy for agricultural diversification and higher value addition within agriculture (Arunachal Pradesh Development Report, 2009). Arunachal Pradesh today produces a variety fruits, vegetables, spices, plantation crops, flowers etc. for commercial purposes.

Objective of study

The study aims to study the changing trend of area, production and productivity horticultural crops in Arunachal Pradesh. The study is empirical in nature based on the secondary data collected from various published and un published sources. The data were collected from various publications of Indian Horticulture Database, National Horticulture Board, Ministry of agriculture, New Delhi and various publications of Statistical Abstract of Arunachal Pradesh, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Government of Arunachal Pradesh and other published and unpublished data available with Directorate of Horticulture, Government of Arunachal Pradesh

Review of Literature

There has been a rapid increase in the production and productivity of horticultural crops in India. In this section review of some of the studies on the area, production and productivity of horticultural crops has been done.

Ahangar and Govindasamy (2013) in their study found that Jammu and Kashmir has great prospect for the horticultural development because of the favourable agro-climatic condition that the State enjoys. There has been an increase in both the area and production of fresh and dry fruit in the State. The production of fruits in the State increased from 9,31,800 metric tonnes from an area of 2,19,039 hectares in 2000-01 to 17,42,142 metric tonnes from an area of 3,47,223 hectares in 2012-13. The area under fresh fruits in the State increased from 1,40,854 hectares in 2000-01 to 2,36,780 hectares in 2012-13 and the area under dry fruits also increased from 78,185 hectares in 2000-01 to 1,10,443 hectares in 2012-13.

Rather et al. (2013) in their study found that the production of fruits particularly apples and walnut increased every year in Jammu and Kashmir. Horticultural sector contributed 7-8 percent of the state GDP and consist of 45 percent of the economic returns in the agricultural sector. The horticultural produce directly influences the income, employment and living standard in the rural areas of the state. The study suggested the government to plan for higher and more quality production. The study also suggested that the state to shift its agricultural development strategy from food security mode to that of value addition by growing high value fruits, vegetables and cash crop.

Jadhav (2013) in his study pointed out that India produces more than 28.2 million tonnes of fruits and 66.00 million tonnes of vegetables and is ranked next to Brazil and China in the world. Horticulture sector witnessed growth of 10.13 percent in production and 4.22 percent in area in 2007-08 over 2006-07. This sector contributed more than 24.5 percent of the agricultural GDP. The study also found that inadequate supply of high quality planting materials, slow adaptability to high yielding variety, lack of post harvest management technology and infrastructure, lack of support price mechanism, poor credit facilities etc were some of the factors responsible for the slow growth of horticulture sector in India.

Thus, many scientific and empirical studies have been conducted in recent on horticultural development in the country. However, there are only a few studies on horticultural development in Arunachal Pradesh. Therefore, the present study is an attempt to study the prospects and production of different horticultural crops in Arunachal Pradesh.

Result and Discussion

Status of Horticultural Sector in Arunachal Pradesh

Arunachal Pradesh located at the eastern most corner of north eastern part of India is considered to be a reservoir of a large variety of horticultural crops like fruits, vegetables, aromatics, spices and flowers. The mountainous topography and the agro climatic condition of the State offers immense scope for growing a variety of horticultural crops that needs to be explored. Horticulture is now a growing economic activity of the people of the state.

Table 1
Production of Horticultural Crops in Arunachal Pradesh

Year	Area (in Hectares)	Production (in Metric Tonnes)
2005-2006	69432	143361
2006-2007	90200	265400
2007-2008	93400	265600
2008-2009	92800	261400
2009-2010	89800	190300
2010-2011	87500	208000
2011-2012	104017	371764
2012-2013	103720	523260
2013-2014	106830	532140
2014-2015	114645	379225
2015-2016	84071.41	362134.98
2016-2017	60729.84	177333.33

Source: Indian horticulture Database from 2008 to 2017.

Statistical Abstract of Arunachal Pradesh from 2000 to 2017.

Thus, the above table reveals that Arunachal Pradesh has witnessed an increasing trend in both area and production of horticultural crops. The state produced 143361 metric tonnes of horticultural crops from an area of 69432 hectares in 2005-06 which increased to 177333.33 metric tonnes from an area of 177333.33 hectares in 2016-2017.

The figure below shows that the productivity of horticultural crops in Arunachal Pradesh fluctuated during the period and increased by only 1.4 times during the period.

Source:-Indian Horticulture Database 2000 to 2017.
Statistical Abstract of Arunachal Pradesh from 2000 to 2017.

Major Horticultural Crops Produced in Arunachal Pradesh

The districts of the Arunachal Pradesh located at different elevation levels enjoy different agro climatic condition, varied soil type and produces a variety of horticultural crops for personal consumption as well as for commercial purposes. The state produces all kinds of horticultural crops like fruits, vegetables, spices, flowers, plantation crops etc and is known for its unique and good quality. A wide range of tropical, sub tropical and temperate fruits such as apple, pine apple, orange, banana, kiwi, plum, jack fruit etc and vegetables like cabbage, cauliflower, potato, tomato, spinach and other edible leafy vegetables and spices like ginger, turmeric, cardamom etc are grown in the state. Floriculture is also another potential economic activity of the State which has gained much popularity over the past few years. Aromatics and medicinal plants, spices like ginger, cardamom, black pepper are also grown for commercial purposes in the State.

The table below shows the major horticultural crops grown in Arunachal Pradesh.

Table 2
Area, Production and Productivity of Horticultural Crops in Arunachal Pradesh, 2016-17

Crop	Area (in hectares)	Production (in metric tonnes)	Productivity (in MT/HT)
Fruits	49846.39	138426.20	2.7
Vegetable	1134.54	11022.07	9.7
Spices	9748.96	27885.06	2.8
Total	60729.89	177333.33	2.9

Source: Statistical Abstract of Arunachal Pradesh, 2017

The State produced 177333.33 metric tonnes of horticultural crops from an area of 60729.890 hectares with a productivity of 2.92 metric tonnes per hectare in the year 2016-17. The production of fruits was highest among the horticultural crops followed by spices and vegetables. The State produced 138426.20 metric tonnes of fruits from an area of 49846.39 hectares with a productivity of 2.7 MT/HA. The State produced

27885.06 metric tonnes of spices from an area of from an area of 9748.96 hectares with a productivity of 2.86 MT/HA. The production of vegetable during the year was 11022.07 metric tonnes from an area of 1134.54 hectares. The figure below shows the percentage share of the horticultural crops during the year.

Fig 2
Percentage Share of Horticultural Crops Produced in Arunachal Pradesh, 2016-2017

Source: Statistical Abstract of Arunachal Pradesh, 2017

The production of fruit comprised of the largest share of 77% of the total production of horticultural crops in the state followed by spices 16% and vegetables 6 %.

Production of Fruits in Arunachal Pradesh

Arunachal Pradesh produces a variety of fruits. The different agro climatic and the geographical condition in the different parts of the state enable it to produce a variety of tropical fruits like orange, pineapple, banana, guava etc and temperate fruits like apple, kiwi, plum, walnut etc. The entire districts of Arunachal Pradesh are known for its production of different kinds of fruits and vegetables. Tawang and West Kameng district is famous for its production of apples, walnut and kiwi, East Kameng, East Siang, west Siang, Upper Subansiri for oranges, Papumpare, Upper Subansiri, Dibang Valley, Lohit, Changlang , Tirap and Longding for pineapple and banana.

Table-3
Area, Production and Productivity of Fruits Produced in Arunachal Pradesh, 2016-17

Fruit	Area (in HA)	Production (in MT)	Productivity (MT/HA)
Citrus	32850.45	79212.50	2.411
Pineapple	2918.77	22952.23	7.863
Apple	6179.38	11665.67	1.887
Banana	2346.56	14650.96	6.243
Kiwi	4022.63	9428.57	2.343
Walnut	1523.60	511.23	0.335
Others	5.00	5.00	1.00
Total	49846.39	138426.20	2.7

Source: Statistical Abstract of Arunachal Pradesh, 2017

Thus, table shows the production of various fruits grown in Arunachal Pradesh. The State produced 138426.20 metric tonnes of fruits from an area of 49846.39 hectares with a productivity of 2.7 metric tonnes per hectares. The production of citrus fruit which was about 57.2 percent of the total fruits produced in the State was highest in the State followed by pine apple (16.5%), banana (10.58%), apple (8.42%) etc. The major Citrus

fruit growing districts are Upper Siang, Roing, Lohit, East Kameng, West Siang, East Kameng, and Upper Subansiri. The production of pineapple ranked second among the fruits produced in the State and is grown in Upper Siang, Roing, Lohit, Papumpare, Upper Subansiri, East Siang and West Siang districts. Bananas are mostly produced in the districts of Lohit, Upper Siang, Roing, Tirap, Longding, Papumpare, East Siang and West Siang. West Kameng, Tawang and Lower Subansiri are major the apple producing districts of the State. Kiwi is another commercial fruit grown in the districts of Tawang, West Kameng, Lower Subansiri and Dibang Valley. The other fruit here includes guava, jack fruit, plum, peach etc.

Conclusion

Arunachal Pradesh though a mountainous state has a huge potential for horticultural crops. However, the commercial production of horticultural crops is at a nascent stage in the State. The State should encourage the people to take up the activity on a large scale for commercial purpose. Horticultural development schemes like National Horticulture Mission should be promoted in the State. Information on the latest technical know how should be disseminated to the farmers to increase their production as well as productivity.

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